

Marxist Critique of Trade Unionism in Colonial Africa: Nigerian Experience

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Abstract

The central theme of this study was to critically examine the nature, origin, role and development of the social movement and institution of trade unionism in colonial Africa from the Marxian perspective. It determined the question whether the role Marxism proposed for unionism had been accomplished and whether it was applicable to colonial Nigeria and by extension, Africa. This study adopted the doctrinal method. It critically analyzed the views of text writers and colonial officials. It examined colonial records and events involving governments, unionists and unionism. It found and held the view that trade union developed with the rise of industrialization but that political unionism was the genre that suited its analysis and critique as against the enterprise or the business union in colonial Africa. The study concluded that trade unionism played a crucial role in the industrial relations atmosphere of colonial Africa and the agitations and struggles leading to the independence of African states including Nigeria.

Keywords: *Marxism on Trade Union, Political Unionism in Colonial Africa, Nigerian Trade Unionism.*

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Introduction

The overriding purpose of the study of trade unionism is to explain its emergence, spread, development and responses to changing times and situations (Allen, 1975 p. 60). Gomez-Mejia, et al (2001, p. 498) have canvassed that unions mean different things in different countries and the labour relations systems of nations vary. Allen (p. 37) has equally opined that the involvement of the state in industrial relations is seen as a means to contain trade unions. Laws regulating labour and its activities have been restrictive, disarming and often oppressive. But as a dynamic social movement in its own right and with strong political overtones, trade unions cannot be explained satisfactorily by either small group studies or psychological studies or in

terms of state or equilibrium analyses. Allen (1975, p. 35) has further shown that the manner in which trade unions developed, the roles they played and their responses to situations are interpreted on the basis of conceptual approach and one such approach conceives industrial relations as occurring within a dynamic situation which is permanent and unalterable as long as the structure remains unaltered.

Conceptual Clarification

Defining and conceptualizing a Trade Union

Three elements are crucial to any definition which distinguishes trade unions from other organizations: the nature of their membership; their purpose and the means they employ to

achieve their purpose. A trade union is any organization whose membership consists of employees, which seeks to organize and represent their interest both in their workplace and society and in particular, seeks to regulate their employment relationship through the direct process of collective bargaining with management (Salamon, 1992 p. 78). The Webbs (cited in Anyanwu, et al, 1997 p. 305) see unions as continuous associations of wage earners for the purpose of maintaining or improving the conditions of their employment. They are permanent and continuing democratic organizations, voluntarily created by workers to protect themselves at their workplace and to improve their working conditions through collective bargaining, membership education, political lobbying and campaigning for effective means of expressing workers' views on social problems.

To Ramalho (1996, p. 14), good trade unions are part of the capitalist reproduction. They are an essential part of the market. It is the nature of trade union action to strengthen capitalism. It is an established, accepted and supportive part of the capitalist system rather than a challenge to it. It is only in market economies that trade unions are possible. According to Begg, et al (1994, p. 208) the traditional view of unions is that they offset the power that a firm enjoys in negotiating wages and working conditions. A single firm has many workers. If each worker were to deal with the firm, the firm can make a take-it-or-leave-it offer. The existence of a union evens up the bargaining process. Once a union is established, it aims not merely to protect its members but to improve their pay and condition. Unions are thus principally designed to affect pay and working conditions.

Trade unions are therefore organizations that act on behalf of employees in negotiations with the employer regarding terms of their employment. It is a lawful assembly, protected by the First Amendment of the Constitution of the USA and Federal and State laws (Brown & Sukys, 1997 p. 536). In Nigeria, every person is entitled to assemble freely and associate with others and in particular he may form or belong to a trade union for the protection of his interests (1999 Constitution & INEC v Musa & Ors).

According to Evans (1956, p. 38), the freedom of working class people to unite together to protect their mutual interest, and to secure a fair share of the wealth they help to produce, is one of those freedoms which distinguishes western democracy from other forms of society. The word 'free' has been increasingly used in connection with trade unions in the west to contrast with the 'un-free' associations of working people in the eastern world which in spite of their lack of freedom, insist on describing themselves as trade unions. But Prandy et al (cited in Salamon, p. 162) have argued that all theories of trade unionism, whether Marxist or not, assume a class ideological posture incorporating the concept of class based upon the market position of labour in production and unionism as the pursuit of class interests.

However, the way men behave is largely determined by their relations to each other and their membership in groups. The important response of the working class to industrialization has been the creation of organizational counterparts to the business enterprise being trade unions. Whenever there is industrialization some kind of trade unionism is found (Broom & Selznick, 1963 p. 15). In other words, trade unions grew as business expanded and technological changes altered the nature of work. Although unions have assumed diverse forms and have served both members and the larger society, they have demanded some protection to help them cope with the changes that made the workplace increasingly impersonal. According to Ramalho (p. 11) experience in Brazil has shown that unions play important in negotiating both industrial and socio-political developments. In fact, they have sought to go beyond the struggle for wage increases to propose and pursue changes in Brazilian society and to deal with problems affecting both labour and society as a whole like poverty, hunger, health, housing, transport, education and income distribution. There is, therefore, a general understanding of a close link between workers' membership of a factory and citizenship of a democracy.

Thus, unions have developed the three-tier aims of protect against lay-offs, improvement of

working conditions and sponsorship of laws to improve the socio-economic and political conditions of workers. Some unions have been primarily political and ideological far more interested in creating a mass base for political change than in establishing good working conditions for members or establishing better working arrangements with employers. This typology of political unionism is mostly likely to occur when organized labour is weak. Unable to win concessions from employers, the unions turn to the political arena. They take the form of a general union which is not strong at the factory level but plays a conspicuous role in politics. It is mostly found in developing countries like Nigeria. Political unionism appears to run contrary to the two categories of trade unions postulated by Otite & Ogionwo (1985, p. 323). They typified trade unionism into industry or company based and cross industry and cross industry based. They, however, acknowledge that in African countries, trade unions play or are made to play political roles. In Congo-Brazzaville, Guinea, Mali and Tanzania, they have acted as militant wings of the government and political parties.

Hoagland (1973, p. 144) has shown that South Africa's Communist Party grew out of the local International Socialist League. The party was founded in 1921 by a group of men like S.P. Bunting who were more English Socialists than Moscow Marxists. The party developed a trade union based on the mines which was one of the reasons it was despised. In Nigeria also, the trade union was equally built around the mines and railway transport sectors which were the largest employers of labour during the colonial times.

However, this typology of political unionism appears not to be restricted to countries like Nigeria. In 1866, the National Labour Union in the USA had turned away from bargaining for better working conditions to political solutions to workers' welfare. A more extreme example of radical unionism in the USA was the Industrial Workers of the World called the Wobblies organized in 1905 which embraced ideas of a number of left-wing groups including Marxists and Syndicalists. The Wobblies hoped to transform society by direct economic action by

taking over major industries and doing away with capitalism.

Statement of the Problem

How did the institution of trade unionism evolve in colonial Africa with particular reference to Nigeria and what critical challenge confronted it in the process of nation building and transition from colonial to independent rule? What role did the genre of political unionism play in the struggle for the attainment of political independence in colonial Africa? Did the trade union play the role in accordance with the prognosis outlined in Marxism?

Methodology

This study was carried out with the doctrinal methodology. Its approach was based on conflict and argumentation. The opinions of text writers, statements and decisions of colonial officers on trade unionism in Africa were used to marry and or confront colonial records, reports and events of the period under study. The outcome of these facts and opinions were used to construct and mirror the Marxist view of the role of political unionism in colonial Africa with references to Nigeria.

Literature Review

Critique of Political Unionism

Until 1946, trade unions were not involved in politics in Nigeria and few politicians and political parties then existing gave serious thought to the immense power of organized labour in nationalist struggles let alone the idea of going all out to utilize the power of unionism (Ananaba, 1969 p. 86). One of the major dynamics of colonialism was that colonial powers were known for pursuing and implementing their 'home' public policies in the colonial dependencies. According to Walter (1987, p. 219), it was an abiding tenet of industrial unions to be non-political. The union was considered an industrial organization and none of its funds was to be used for any political purpose whatsoever. Any member raising any political issue at any meeting was to be warned to desist and on insistence, expelled from the union. Along with opposition to political action

went opposition to industrial action. None of the industrial unions was ever allowed to call a strike.

In 1926, George Spencer of the Spencer Union had stated that a strike was an experiment in elementary communism. William Gregory had even stated that the main principles and programmes of his trade union were disbelief in strikes, cooperation with employers and fight against communism. For him, it was a fight for the freedom, protection and liberty of the great British Empire. It is, therefore, not surprising, according to Ekeh-Momoh (2004, p. 43), that the first union, America Federation of Labour in 1886 listed as one of its principles, the acceptance of capitalism.

Although western society is founded on intense freedom, individualism and liberal democracy, trade unions were initially formed in the USA and Britain with radical political policies pursued with the aim of reforming the society. Membership of a trade was the finest asset a worker could have. It was not only the source through which the worker could make known his grievances, improve his wages, add weight to his social status, claim equality and give protection to his family, it was difficult to understand any worker having a leaning towards a non-political organization when his very life depended on politics. For instance, the British Labour Party was founded as a result of the decision of the Trade Union Congress in 1899 to establish an electoral and parliamentary organization to ensure the election of working class representatives to parliament (Tayo, 1992 p. 150). For Fisher & Dix (p. 144) the foundation of parliamentary democracy was to expose wealth and privilege to the attack of the people. It was a sword pointed at the heart of property power. Democracy was, therefore, not only a form of government but a type of society which requires the conversion of economic power into society and the resolute elimination of all forms of special privileges which favour some groups and disfavour others.

In other words, the solutions to the problems of the working class are to come through political action. And for socialists, political action cannot be merely a matter of electoral organization to secure a majority in parliament nor can it be

considered as just a matter of power. It is a matter of the establishment and application of political power for the transformation of property relations in society. According to Gourevitch (1986, p. 42), socialist orthodoxy calls for the elimination of the owners of capital.

But the major critique of political unionism in Nigeria, and by extension Africa, is whether the formation of the early trade unions was actuated by political motives and considerations. Submitting that trade unions generally emerged from efforts of workers to seek an improvement of existing conditions through collective action, Ananaba (p. 10) has held that it is doubtful whether such efforts, motives and consideration actuated the formation of the Southern Nigerian Civil Service Union in 1912. According to Tayo (p.33) it was not typically a trade union in that it was not formed with all the ideals of a trade union that felt the need to fight for members' right nor was it formed out of frustration or disaffection with its members' employment conditions. To Yesufu (cited in Ananaba, p. 10), it was also not formed by a group of dissatisfied workers who wanted a platform from which to fight for amelioration of grievances or for the improvement of specific conditions of employment. It was merely to match the existence of such an institution in Sierra Leone and provide a forum for social interaction among African officers in the colonial service.

The foregoing may, however, appear to be a general position. There are indications from Ananaba (p. 11) that civil servants were treated by the colonial establishment like indentured apprentices who signed agreements with the colonial government with emphasis on the duties and obligations of the workers than his rights and privileges. There were indications that workers were fined for lateness to work and deductions were made for unauthorized absence from work. In fact, racial discrimination was one of the subjects discussed by the inaugural congress of the National Congress of British West Africa in 1920. There was no doubt that Africans could hardly rise above the position of a clerk. And when qualified and appointed to a European post, he could not be paid the salary of a European. On the other hand, colour was an asset and a passport for quick attention for

Association of European Civil Servants members of which were treated with remarkable speed whenever their grievances came up for consideration. According to Freund (1988, pp. 91-92), the trade union movement succeeded typically in organizing labour which also had economic grievances but which was much concerned with racial differentials in payment, promotion and treatment that suggested radical objection to the colonial state. Thus, labour found its future prospects in developing nationalist movements whose agitations they helped to sustain.

Results and Discussion

State and Political Unionism in Colonial Africa

The question that arises for consideration is the relationship between nationalism, the State and trade unionism. According to Nwankwo (1985, p. 24) labour unions loyalties may be motivated by self-interest, but nationalism is always motivated by selfless loyalty to the nation. Labour loyalties are subordinate to nationalism because if the nation or state does not exist, labour unions cannot. A labour union exists because there is a territorial boundary where some economic activities in a particular sector generate a sense of unity of purpose amongst the workers. As a matter of fact, labour unions in Africa seemed to be the link between nationalist politics and a mass, urban base. It was an arm of the nationalist movement. Strikes and union activities seemed to provide the most disciplined of the popular weapons on which nationalist politics could rest in pre and post-independent Africa (Freund, p. 18). Little distinction was drawn between workers' reaction and consciousness on the one hand and nationalism and anti-colonial politics on the other hand. It was assumed that they represented part of the great stream (Freund, pp. 21-22).

As canvassed by Ananaba (p. 34) the selection of Michael Imoudu as one of those for the Pan-Nigeria London delegation brought organized labour into the vanguard of nationalist struggle for independence as he and his followers identified themselves with politics through their membership of the Zikist movement which desired that organized labour should be closely

identified with the struggles for independence despite official opposition. The Trade Union Congress was then brought into the mainstream of the National Congress for Nigeria and Cameroon and was to continue as such until the formation of its proposed Labour Party (Ananaba, p. 92). Moreover, the leaders of the Trade Union Congress of Nigeria had spoken of plans by certain persons to introduce the dictatorship of the proletariat after the achievement of independence (Ananaba, p. 190). It was reported in 1960 that a Nigerian trade union leader had concluded plans with certain foreign power by which the latter was to supply financial and material aids, including arms, to strengthen the struggles for the workers of Nigeria which struggles were to begin after independence and the aids were to be made available when certain countries had established diplomatic relations with Nigeria and opened embassies in Lagos (Ananaba, 191).

By 1963, the first annual conference of United Labour Congress had adopted a resolution to set up a political action committee whose primary objective was the propagation of a socialist welfare state and the furtherance of the workers' power and influence in the national politics of Nigeria (Ananaba, 237). The congress had also addressed and discussed a programme of trade union action which was to bring the world trade union movement under the influence of international communism through various devices. Amongst the devices was the Leninist advocacy of use of all stratagems and artifices, adoption of illegal methods, occasional silence, occasional concealment of truth, for the sole purpose of penetrating the trade union, remaining therein and carrying out the communist assignment (Ananaba, p. 211). By the early 1940s a Marxist group or a communist front organization had been established of which Nduka Eze was a member. The group held the view that it must infiltrate important organizations, amongst them, political parties and trade unions (Ananaba, p. 143).

The state is an actor in the industrial relations system and its roles have assumed increased importance because it is the only political organization of society that has authority to regulate the activities of all other groups in the

society for the purpose of maintaining law and order, social justice, liberty and social order. It, therefore, maintains industrial peace and harmony in the workplace through the machinery of government and public agencies. The position of the state as the single largest employer compliments its sovereign power and control of industrial relations (Tayo, p. 19). The role of the colonial state in labour was to redress the imbalance between labour and employers (Tayo, p.91). Thus the Trade Union Ordinance of 1938 conferred legal status on unions. But early labour policies of the colonial state in Africa and by contraction Nigeria, were dictated not by concern for effective bilateral relationship between labour and capital but by social and economic conditions such as attempts by colonialists to contain workers' disaffection and growing social disorders arising from the economic problems of the two world wars and nationalism resulting in increased workers' consciousness and rapid increase in unionization.

The four principal factors that encouraged unionism, according to Tayo, were public policy, nationalism, industrial structure and international division and factionalism. Anyanwu et al (1997) on the other hand canvassed that the growth was positively influence by inflation and tended towards a system of numerous, small financially weak organizations. There was fractionalization and bitter rivalry between trade union federations. Another factor that aided the development was the repressive measures of the colonial government as exemplified in the Burutu Shooting incident, the Iva Valley Shooting incident and the conscription of Kings College students into the army due to their strike.

Colonial Labour Policy and Trade Unionism

It was with the advent of European imperialism in Africa that a consistent attitude towards labour in scholarly literature can be conversed. This in turn feeds contemporary debates on the historiography of labour. The labour policy of the African colonial states vacillated between voluntarism and interventionism. However, state intervention in labour relations has become far more dominant till present day because, as

for voluntarism, what is clear is that its days have gone and what the future has for it is extended legal framework of state interventionism (Jones, 1989 p. 91).

In 1930, Lord Passfield, Secretary of State for the Colonies (cited in Ananaba, pp. 21-22), had regarded the formation of unions as a natural and legitimate consequence of social and industrial process. But His Lordship also recognized that there was a danger that, without sympathetic supervision and guidance and without experience of combinations, organization of labourers may fall under the domination of disaffected persons, by which their activities may be diverted to improper and mischievous ends. Thus, according to Freund (p. 94) the Trade Union Congress of Britain seconded organizers to the African colonies partly to create what was described as responsible, systematic and non-political unions and partly to combat the incursions of communism.

One of the interventionist acts of the colonial state in Nigeria was in 1938. Under pressure from the British Colonial Office, the Colonial Administration in Nigeria passed the Trade Union Ordinance leading to the formation of not less than twelve workers' organizations and registration of fourteen unions. The Ordinance was a landmark in the history of modern trade unionism in Nigeria. It did not only legalize unionism, it saw the beginning of a coherent public labour policy of interventionism in Nigeria (Tayo, p. 34). Elsewhere in Africa, the position was largely different. In Kenya, unions were vigorously controlled by government. Until 1943, they enjoyed no official recognition and those organizing them were always open to prosecution for conspiracy. Evans (p. 38) cited the case of a young Indian trade union leader, Mr. Makhan Singh. Despite the ban on the East African Trade Union Congress which was unregistered, Mr. Singh continued to organize it. Singh was an open and avowed communist. He was placed on restricted order in Lokitaung. He was tagged an 'undesirable'. His restriction was based on conduct of the manner calculated to raise discontent and disaffection among the inhabitants of the colony. He appealed. His appeal to the Privy Council was dismissed and

the order was upheld as he engaged in political opinions that were calculated to raise discontent and disaffection.

Acting for the colonial state of Nigeria under the Nigerian General Defence Regulation, 1941, Governor Bourdillon, while restricting Michael Imoudu, stated that he was satisfied that it was necessary to prevent him from acting in a manner prejudicial to public safety and defence (Hoagland, p. 190 & Freund, p. 127). In South African, the colonial state added the colour bar. The most important control over African wages was the legal prohibition against Africans bargaining collectively for wages. Only employees of registered unions could bargain with their employers as a group. The law excluded Africans from the category of employees and government did not register union that had Africans as members until 1979. Most employers openly opposed giving Africans the right to form effective unions. It was also illegal for Africans to strike for any reason.

In other words, the colonial state and its industrial employers were reluctant to the acceptance of trade unionism in their dependencies and establishments. They mostly believed in the theory of the divine rights of management to which labour unions were dialectically opposed (Ananaba, p. 74). Where the colonial state and its industrial concerns had been persuaded to tolerate unions, they laid down stringent conditions which the unions had to fulfill before they could be recognized and dealt with. To be lawful, a trade union would have the approval of the Registrar of Trade Unions. Such a registration could be refused and registration was invariably withdrawn from break-away unions. The Registrar's control was so firm that it could revoke a certificate of registration.

In cases in which the African workers and labour leaders had shown sufficient resistance against the colonial state and its industrial concerns, they were met with the full weight of the law or even brutal force and state violence. The Enugu or the Iva Valley shooting incident of 1949 was one of the most significant episodes in the history of Nigerian labour. In terms of the losses sustained, the emotion excited and the grief created in the

public mind, no industrial dispute in Nigeria can be matched with it. Crowds rioted in Aba, Port Harcourt, Onitsha and Calabar against the killing of twenty-one defenseless miners on strike and the wounding of fifty-one others. According to Ananaba (p.98), the industrial relations between workers and the Colliery management had long been strained partly due to the poor human relations existing between the European officers and their Nigerian subordinates and partly due to the management's opposition to the existence of a militant or political unionism in the Colliery.

Apparently, it was the suspicion that some sort of alliance existed between the miners and political agitators that convinced the Chief Commissioner that the events in the Colliery were no longer an industrial dispute. It was argued by the colonial state that the shooting was to prevent explosives from falling into the hands of subversive elements. Concluding on the incident, Ananaba (p. 110) submitted that the incident partly made nationalists to change their political slogan to 'self-government for Nigeria now'. Earlier, there had been the shooting of workers of the United African Company in Burutu. Addressing the Burutu incident in 1947, Cole (cited in Ananaba, p. 72) had submitted that the colonial state was using all means, fair and foul, to dwarf the growth of trade union movement in Nigeria.

The colonial state intervention in the trade union movement was equally expressed in censorship. Though majority of Nigerian workers were oriented to the west and were not interested in the cold war between the east and the west, Ananaba has pointed out that colonial policy and the general political climate were not conducive to an easy flow of Marxist philosophy. In fact soon after the announcement of the circulation of the 'Nigerian Worker', it came under censorship in 1944. The official statement of the censorship was that the magazine contained incorrect statements or allegation of facts and hard repeatedly contained unfair and unjustified comments and that such statements, allegations and criticism were likely to excite disaffection and create or encourage discontent against government of Nigeria.

But labour policy of the Nigerian colonial state was also paternalistic. For example, the 1945 general strike whose immediate cause was the unwillingness of the colonial state to honour its pledges over the cost of living allowance review in accordance with the cost of living index was one of the most important events in Nigeria labour history lasting for 45 to 52 days with more than 150,000 workers participating. The Tudor Davies Commission which came as a result of the aftermath of the strike had observed that a number of workers' organizations registered as trade unions were mere house associations which would not have been recognized as trade unions either by the British Trade Union Congress or the International Trade Union Movement.

In the foregoing regard, Sir Authur Richards, the then Colonial Governor, had stated that his government was partly to blame for it was more than probable that the wise advice at the time the unions were at their infancy would have guided unions into the recognition of the main principles of trade unionism. But unfortunately, trade unions were allowed to develop on the lines of a family council, or friendly society composed of all the employees of one firm or person and in some instances, the employer himself became the leader of the union. According to him, for the unions to get over this 'teething problem', they needed not only sympathetic encouragement but the sort of help given to the British working class by prominent humanists.

Yet, this was the same strike that was lauded as having shaken the nation to its foundations as never had Nigerian workers demonstrated such impregnable solidarity and never had they been more united in opposition to the bad faith and the injustices of the colonial state. For Freund (p. 92), what made the national strike of 1945 so effective and threatening to the colonial state was its concentration among workers in the transport and communication sectors essential to the colonial economy. Thus the trade unions were important both because strike in the strategic sectors could cripple the extractive economy and the normal running of administration and because of their potential for organizational discipline which was often lacking

in other kinds of institutions or organizations, as a result, there was a marked struggle for political control of trade unions in the colonies in the immediate pre-independence years.

Conclusion

This study critiques the origin, role and development of trade union in Africa under colonialism. It holds that although trade unionism may have predated the colonial era, the advent of industrialization in Europe threw up the need for market outside Europe for finished products of the industries and the need to tap the vast natural resources of the new worlds particularly Africa to feed the industries with raw materials. This led to the establishment of colonial rule and imperialism. This era was crucial in the struggle of the trade union for recognition and liberation from suppression and active participation in nationalism. The struggle for political independence did not only show the trade union as a tool for political agitation as conceived in Marxism, but also as a polarized tool. The polarities were not only along colour and partisan lines, but equally ideologically impelled such that the international supremacy between the systems of capitalist and socialist states became the defining moment of trade union loyalties in colonial Africa. While these currents were on, the colonial states' interventionist and paternalistic policies in terms of labour suppression and management were equally on the mainstream agenda of the colonial states till the arrival of independence in the 1960s.

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